

Book review: Methods for Collecting Insects and other Terrestrial Arthropods, Vol. I

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ABSTRACT. For a long period, the Iranian entomologists followed a rather narrow spectrum of methods to collect arthropods that are described in taxonomic papers. Recently, this knowledge gap was filled with the publication of a book entitled “Methods for Collecting Insects and other Terrestrial Arthropods”. The book efficiently describes 110 collecting methods in 18 chapters and 468 pages and it contains as well a huge collection of more than 300 illustrations and a considerable set of references. It is highly recommended for both students, professional entomologists and academic personnel.

Key words: Arthropods, Entomology, Modern tools, Habitats, Sampling trips, Taxonomy, Museums

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As a Ph.D. student of Entomology, I remember my first attempts on collecting some insects for a class project in late 2007 based on some manuals of that time. However, I realized soon that the collecting methods are diverse and several of them not well-defined. As an Iranian entomologist, I have a general knowledge about most common methods (e.g., Malaise trap, light trap, sweeping net). However, any collecting method should be efficacious on the target organisms. Nowadays, methods of collecting arthropods in Iran are getting organized towards this direction. Therefore, there was an urgent need of a comprehensive manual on arthropod-collection methods, an issue however, that was highly challenging.

The new book, *Methods for Collecting Insects and other Terrestrial Arthropods (MCITA)*, in Persian, provides thorough information about numerous methods. The author of the book, Prof. Dr Ehsan Rakhshani is a well-known and qualified entomologist in Iran working with Hymenoptera for more than 17 years. There are several previous and up-to-date described methods in his book, which undoubtedly increase our knowledge regarding arthropods sampling. The MCITA treats 110 methods of collecting arthropods that have been included in volume I. This volume reports 18 chapters with an introduction for each one and then a complete description of different sampling methods. The MCITA has 322

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qualitative illustrations, many of them acquired by the research team of the author of the book along with comprehensive explanations about handling the captured arthropods.

In the introduction, the author provides basic information about the importance of arthropods in nature, general information on how they can be collected and the aim of the book. Chapters 1–3 deal with the design of sampling procedures, habitats sites of collection and sampling under field conditions. In these chapters, the author presents a list of the equipment that is necessary for arthropods' collecting and then followed by descriptions of all the main collecting methods: by hand in different habitats, pitfall trapping, sweep net sampling and so on. Information about the best time to collect arthropods, with regard to different habitats and seasons is also provided. Chapters 4–18 explain the link between collection of arthropods and research. All chapters are fully referenced. There is detailed reference upon previous methods and how they were updated.

This manual will increase noticeably the amount of studies on collecting arthropods in Iran especially insects, from taxonomic,

biodiversity, ecological and biological point of views. The publication of this book is an extremely important event for the Iranian entomologists, and it will doubtless set a benchmark reference work in the forthcoming future. Volume I is a valuable addition to the library of any broad-minded entomologist or naturalist, and should be hosted in University libraries throughout Iran. Meanwhile, volume II and III are anticipated for the completion of the set. In my opinion, the book will be of great interest among Persian-speaking readers.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

کتاب‌گزاری: روش‌های جمع‌آوری حشرات و سایر بندپایان خشکی‌زی (جلد اول)

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چکیده: در یک دوره‌ی طولانی مدت، جمع‌آوری کننده‌های حشرات و سایر بندپایان خشکی‌زی در ایران خودشان را به برخی روش‌ها و ابزارهای عمومی در برخی مقالات تاکسونومیک، محدود کرده بودند. در حال حاضر، این فضای خالی با انتشار یک کتاب درباره‌ی روش‌های جمع‌آوری حشرات و بندپایان خشکی‌زی پر شده است. این کتاب ۱۱۰ روش جمع‌آوری را در ۱۸ فصل و ۴۶۸ صفحه توصیف کرده و شامل مجموعه‌ای بزرگ و قابل توجهی از منابع و بیش از ۳۰۰ تصویر می‌باشد. بنابراین، این کتاب به دانشجویان، حشره‌شناسان متخصص و کارشناسان دانشگاهی بسیار توصیه می‌شود.

واژگان کلیدی: بندپایان، حشره‌شناسی، ابزارهای نوین، زیستگاه‌ها، سفرهای نمونه‌برداری، تاکسونومی، موزه‌ها